

D5.3 – Blue-Cloud Services Uptake Report

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Executive summary

Blue-Cloud has achieved significant results since the start of the Blue-Cloud project in October 2019. The Blue-Cloud Open Science platform introduced a “de facto” federation taking place at 3 levels: the data, the computing resources and the analytical services. For each of them Blue-Cloud orchestrated mechanisms that successfully established interoperability and resulted in a Data Discovery and Access Service, the Virtual Research Environment and five Virtual Laboratories providing access to 15 services. Blue-Cloud working environments are serving more than 1,300 users in total spread across 20 countries. Up to mid February 2023, more than 42,100 working sessions have been executed, with an average of 1,027 working sessions per month and an average of 294 working analytics sessions executed every month by the users of the VLabs.

This document gives an overview of the main services released by the project - the Virtual Research Environment, the five VLabs and the Data Discovery and Access services - and for each of them presents the main target users, the exploitation of the services. Statistics about the growth of users is presented, with explanations commenting on the type of services exploited and reasons behind the evolution of the user base as well as on the works performed.

The document also highlights the *exploitation potential* for the Blue-Cloud services, detailing what scientific advances the solutions introduced can offer to the wider marine community, and what type of usage can be done for the services when coupled with other applications and solutions, additional datasets and exported to other communities. For those Virtual labs whose services and datasets were exploited by the participants to the Blue-Cloud hackathon, a short overview of the main outcomes is also provided, since the work that these teams performed is illustrative of the potential impact that can be generated thanks to the exploitation of the Blue-Cloud infrastructure.

Chapter 1 illustrates the overall usage and uptake of the Blue-Cloud open science platform by its partners

Chapter 2 is dedicated to the uptake and exploitation of the services offered by the Blue-Cloud demonstrators as part of their Virtual Laboratories

Chapter 3 illustrates the usage of the Data Discovery and Access Service

Chapter 4 introduces the exploitation potential linked to the usage of the solutions by third party communities, such in the case of the JERICO Research Infrastructure.

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1. Introduction - overall exploitation of Blue-Cloud open science platform

The Blue-Cloud VRE¹ features a set of useful services and components (i.e., cloud storage, computing resources, collaborative workspace, R-Studio, JupyterHub, Software Importer, Analytics Engine, Catalogue), enabling users to create Virtual Labs (VLabs) for collaborating on an activity by sharing materials and communicating in a smart and flexible way. Using the Blue-Cloud VLabs, users are able to further exploit the data collected and accessed via the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access Service following a FAIR data (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) approach, as well as using data sets provided through other repositories and infrastructures, including those ingested by users themselves.

As of M41, February 2023, **the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment hosts 1519 aggregated users, with accesses from 84 countries, achieving the expected targets of 1.000 users from 25 countries.**

The graph below shows the evolution of the VRE community from M19 to M41. As for monthly accesses, they peaked as expected with the preparation and execution of the Blue-Cloud Hackathon in January and February 2022, while moving to a slower but steady growth towards the end of the project and the lead-up to the following Horizon Europe Blue-Cloud 2026.

Figure 1 Aggregated users and accesses in Blue-Cloud VRE from Feb 2021 to February 2023

As expected for a pilot project, accesses were prevalent in the countries where consortium partners had stronger networks and links to existing research communities, e.g. Italy, Belgium and France, but proportions have gradually changed as we can see in the graphs below, comparing the pre-Hackathon accesses with the ones from the last leg of the project, when Blue-Cloud increasingly became a well-known project in the ecosystem.

¹ <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/>

Figure 2 Country breakout of Blue-Cloud VRE sessions by period

As reported in D4.6² *Blue Cloud VRE Operation Report*, 36.4% of the users come from 100 Universities; 13.8% of the users belong to 38 International Organizations; 35.6% of the users belong to 98 National Organizations; 14.2% of the users exploited a commercial email provider (e.g., Gmail).

Figure 3. Users Provenance

1.1. Blue-Cloud Lab

In addition to the VLabs for the Blue-Cloud demonstrators described later on in Chapter 2, those users exploited also the Blue-Cloud services as available in a common community VLab: the so called generic Blue-Cloud Lab³. This VLab was created in October 2019 to provide the Blue-Cloud community at large with a working environment to experiment with Blue-Cloud common facilities,

² Available from the Blue-Cloud catalogue here <https://data.d4science.net/MHCE>

³ <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/web/blue-cloudlab>

without the need to have a custom laboratory or as a playground for a potential new, target lab. The Blue-Cloud Lab is open access and the number of users making use of it reached 259 In February 2023. The figure below displays the growing trend of the number of users exploiting the Blue-Cloud Lab since the initial release.

Figure 3 Blue-Cloud Lab Number of Users

1.2. Blue-Cloud Data and Service Catalogue

Stakeholders: Data Infrastructures & Horizontal e-Infrastructures, Academia and Researchers, Policy & Funding bodies, International Organisations, Relevant EU-funded projects & initiatives, Influencers, hacktivists, NGO's & general public

The Catalogue is part of the Blue-Cloud VRE and describes data products and information products resulting from the Blue-Cloud V Labs together with the provenance metadata about methods and input data sets used to generate these resulting products.

The Catalogue is a fundamental component for the FAIRness of the Blue-Cloud VRE as it allows users of V Labs to publish very diverse typologies of research outputs and make them seamlessly discoverable. In particular, the Catalogue is exploited to publish the Blue-Cloud Services and exchange them with the EOSC Marketplace Services Catalogue so that EOSC users can discover and access the V Lab and their services.

Moreover, the Catalogue ensures direct publication on items into the Blue-Cloud Zenodo

community⁴.

Welcome to the Blue-Cloud Catalogue!

Here you will find data, products, and resources of interest for the Blue-Cloud community.

In particular, the Catalogue features datasets and products resulting from the Blue-Cloud Virtual Laboratories and the methods used to generate them.

Every Catalogue item is accompanied by rich descriptions capturing general attributes to enhance FAIRness:

- title and creator(s)
- accessibility properties
- technical properties, e.g. size and format
- legal and ethical attributes, e.g. whether containing personal data
- intellectual properties, e.g. licences

Browse the Blue-Cloud Catalogue now!

Items Search

[See All Items](#) [See All Tags](#)

Blue-Cloud Catalogue statistics

56	10	11	5
items	virtual labs	groups	types

Browse by Virtual Labs

Blue-Cloud Lab (3)				
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Figure 4 Screenshot of the Blue-Cloud Service Catalogue

Overall, up to February 2023 the catalogue received a total of 2687 queries leading to 3161 page views of single item pages and 462 access to the actual resource the item represents. These numbers are destined to grow, e.g. in the March 2023 only the catalogue served 100 queries, 135 item page views and 32 item accesses from Blue-Cloud partners.

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/communities/bluecloud/>

2. Uptake of Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs and their services

During the Blue-Cloud project, the multi-disciplinary **Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs**⁵ were configured with specific analytical workflows serving the real-life demonstrators developed. These Blue-Cloud V Labs showcase (reproducible) analytical methods and workflows that have been developed to support marine researchers across different thematic areas, and have been adopted and adapted for inputs and analyses according to the needs of the experiments performed by the Blue-Cloud partners leading the aforementioned demonstrators, as well as some initial external users coming mainly through the Hackathon and the collaboration with some third party initiatives such as JERICO.

Figure 5 Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs and the datasets that they retrieve

Between February 2021, when the V Labs were first launched, and February 2023, users of the Virtual Labs and their services have started growing, from the initial user base composed of the project partners, up to 567 registered users⁶ over the five virtual labs. The graph below documents the growth demonstrating an evident interest in the services made available by the various labs.

⁵ <https://blue-cloud.org/vlabs>

⁶ In February 2023: the V Lab “Zoo- and Phytoplankton Essential Ocean Variable products” had 140 registered users, the V Lab “Plankton Genomics” had 55 registered users, the V Lab “Marine Environmental Indicators” had 183 registered users, the V Lab “Fish, a matter of scales” services had 35 registered users in Fisheries Atlas and 14 registered in GRSF-pre, the V Lab “Aquaculture Monitor” had 140 registered users in the Aquaculture Atlas Generation.

Figure 6 Increase of users per Virtual Lab from Feb 2021 to Feb 2023

In the chapters below a description of usage and uptake of the services offered within each Virtual Labs are presented. Per each VLab a short overview of the demonstrator is provided, with special focus on the main target users and the response that each of them is giving with respect to the UN Sustainable development Goals. Statistics about the growth of users is presented per each VLab, with explanations commenting on the type of services exploited and reasons behind the evolution of the user base.

For those Virtual labs whose services and datasets were also exploited by the participants to the Blue-Cloud hackathon, a short overview of the main outcomes is also provided. From 7 to 9 February 2022, 149 marine scientists and researchers, data scientists, ICT experts, innovators, students, and passionate about the Ocean from 73 countries and grouped in 32 teams joined the Blue-Cloud Hackathon. They explored and tested the Blue-Cloud Open Science platform to develop applications that contribute to improving knowledge of marine ecosystems; support the transition to a greener, blue economy; advance Ocean literacy; and/or enhance international collaboration towards achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations Agenda 2030. A total of 23 Teams completed the challenge, representing 111 participants. The work that these teams performed and the impact generated thanks to the exploitation of the Blue-Cloud infrastructure is referred to in each of the dedicated Virtual labs.

2.1. VLab “Zoo- and Phytoplankton Essential Ocean Variable products”

The Virtual Lab “Zoo- and Phytoplankton Essential Ocean Variable products” provides a description of the current state of plankton communities and forecasts their evolution, representing valuable information for the modelling, assessment and management of the marine ecosystems.

Partners:

Main Target Users: Plankton researchers, ocean modellers, data product developers and Blue Data infrastructures, for their data products catalogues and as use cases

UN SDGs addressed: 13 Climate action, 14 Life below water

The Vlab offers three independent services that consist of the combination of different data types (biological, physical and environmental data) to then apply models that generate an output. These are offered in a working space where data and scripts are accessible and reusable. The offered services are:

- **Zooplankton Essential Ocean Variable:** Zooplankton EOV generates zooplankton gridded maps of six zooplankton species in the North East Atlantic. The workflow uses the DIVAnd software tool (Data Interpolating Variational Analysis in n dimensions) that allows to interpolate sparse in situ measurements onto a regular grid in an optimal way.
- **Phytoplankton Essential Ocean Variable:** Phytoplankton EOV generates global open ocean 3D gridded products of (1) chlorophyll a concentration (Chla), which is a proxy of the total phytoplankton biomass, and (2) Phytoplankton Functional Types (PFT), as a proxy for phytoplankton diversity, based on temperature and salinity in situ data matched up with ocean color satellite products.
- **Modelling phyto & zooplankton interactions:** Modelling phyto and zooplankton interactions enables users to calculate the relative contribution that limits the growth of phytoplankton by the drivers: nutrients, phosphates, silicates, light and zooplankton grazing.

Data sources through Blue-Cloud

This VLab has been developed by exploiting the following data sources from the Blue-Cloud DD&AS or directly from the data repository.

Blue-Cloud interoperable data space Vlab "Zoo- and Phytoplankton EOv products"

		Zooplankton abundances
		Salinity and temperature
		Satellite-derived reflectance, Satellite sea level anomaly, Temperature and salinity, MLD Global ARMOR 3D
		BGC-Argo Float
		Bathymetry data
		Chla, Nutrients, Temperature and Photosynthetically Active Radiation

Figure 7 Zoo- and phytoplankton EOv products data sources from the Blue-Cloud DD&AS

2.1.1. User trend

As of the end of March 2023 there are 143 users registered to the VLab. This number increased exponentially during the first 2 years of the project, with a peak around January 2022, and continued growing steadily over the last year, where the developing phase of the VLab was concluded. This is also observed on the number of monthly access to the Vlab (Figure 5) that is lower but stable during the last 6 months.

Figure 8 Number of users registered to the Vlab since the beginning

On average there were 213 monthly accesses to the Vlab between February 2022 and March 2023, with a maximum of 423 monthly accesses in June and a minimum of 94 monthly accesses in September 2022 (Figure 5). When breaking down the number of monthly accesses to the Vlabs in the different services, we observed that the monthly accesses to Jupyter Hub, (Figure 6) are considerably higher than the monthly accesses to R studio (Figure 7). Over the last year there were on average 47 accesses to Jupyter Hub, with a peak of 138 in June 2022. While R studio was accessed on average 10 times per month. This can be explained because 2 of the data products developed in this Vlab make use of Jupyter notebooks and only one uses R studio. Nevertheless, the high difference indicates that these are the products that have been used more.

Figure 8: Figure 9 Number of users registered to the Vlab since the beginning.

Figure 10 Monthly number of accesses to JupyterHub from March 2022 to March 2023

Figure 11 Monthly number of accesses to R studio from March 2022 to March 2023

2.1.2. Uptake, exploitation and exploitation potential of the services

All data, methods and outputs have been published in the Blue Catalogue at this link: https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/group/zoo-phytoplankton_eov/catalogue. The input data used in the products is available for long term and as long as the data repository exists, by the following Blue Data Infrastructures (BDI): EMODnet Biology/EurOBIS, CMEMS, SeaDataNet, GEBCO and the World Ocean Atlas. Input data outside of the BDIs, is accessible from the Vlab. Furthermore, some of the products can also be accessed from external platforms to maximise the exploitation of the results.

- The **phytoplankton EOVS product** has been used to update the Copernicus product with DOI <https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00046>, that is published in the data catalogue from CMEMS: https://resources.marine.copernicus.eu/product-detail/MULTIOBS_GLO_BIO_BGC_3D_REP_015_010/INFORMATION
- **Zooplankton Essential Ocean Variable product** is published in Zenodo and linked to the git hub:
 - Barth, Alexander, & Troupin, Charles (2022). BlueCloud-Plankton: v1.0.1 (v1.0.1). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7053067>
 - Barth, Alexander, & Troupin, Charles (2022). DIVAnd-BlueCloud-Plankton: v1.0.1 (v1.0.1). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7041170>
- **Modelling phyto & zooplankton interactions**: can also be accessed from zenodo: Steven Pint, & Viviana Otero. (2021). Data, scripts and model output to perform spatiotemporal analysis of plankton drivers in the Belgian part of the North Sea [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6794084>. This model will be expanded in Blue Cloud 2026 in the Carbon-Plankton dynamics Vlab.

This Blue Cloud VLab through the three services developed shows its capability to **use several datasets from different sources**. Other and additional sources can be used and run for the same services and the services could be used on other VREs as the ones that will be developed and displayed in the future improvements of the European operational services, data aggregators and Digital Twin of the Ocean for example to study different “what if” scenarios. Therefore this prototype is useful and complementary to the present and future marine services as it is able to use data and products from these services and to provide a good example of possible Blue Cloud VLab that can be transferred and adapted to these services.

Moreover, the phytoplankton EOVS service developed during the project provided an updated 3D gridded product, made of in situ and satellite data, that has been **integrated in the last release of the Copernicus Marine Service catalogue**.

2.1.3. Hackathon exploitation potential

The best examples of usage of this Vlab are those from the hackathon.

The **VLIZ BlueCloudHackathon** team, lead by VLIZ, reproduced the zooplankton EOVS product with different data sources using the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery & Access service to create interpolated maps of some of the most common phytoplankton species in the North East Atlantic. This team was composed of two IT specialists and one marine biologist, from which we can say that the service provided in this Vlab can easily be reproduced by non experts.

The other example corresponds to one of the awarded teams: the "[Wildlife Tracker for Oceans](#)".

This application is a geo-framework dedicated to the real-time assessment of Marine Protected Areas - MPAs. The software is able to retrieve live feeds from Satellite Constellations like Argos for animal tracking and Copernicus for ocean bio-physic data. It allows users to visualise the movements of marine megafauna with a real-time feed. **With the support of the Blue-Cloud Hackathon, the Wildlife Tracker for Oceans includes now the hotspot of Phytoplankton concentration, with different levels of depth, data that was derived in the Phytoplankton EOVI product.**

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 3rd Place application

The "Wildlife Tracker for Ocean" team joined the **Challenge 1A: Understanding the Ocean - How might we map hotspots of plankton diversity and identify geographic gaps in our knowledge using currently available plankton data sets?** Due to the outstanding quality of work performed, the "Wildlife Tracker for Ocean" team won the 3rd prize in the Blue-Cloud Hackathon.

Team members:

- Bryan Vallejo (Ecuador) - Team Lead
- Tran Ngo (Vietnam) - Blue Economy Director
- Sofia Green (Ecuador) - Conservation and Marine Resources
- Ederson Enriquez (Ecuador) - Content Creator

"Wildlife Tracker for Ocean" offers the following three services:

- **Real-time alerts:** Once the biologging data is connected to their database and the Wildlife Tracker is retrieving real-time data the alert system is connected. Alerts are customisable e.g. individuals out of MPAs, on land, or in high fishing pressure zones. Alerts are received via mobile.
- **Customisable visualisation:** Wildlife Tracker enables users to customise the visualisation based on selected individuals and selected satellite data. The map animation can be downloaded as a web map that can be uploaded to our website and a web map gallery is created for specific purposes.
- **Environmental eco-annotation:** The new enrichment algorithm annotates each location and date with historic spatio-temporal data generated from remote sensors. This product helps scientists to understand wildlife behaviour and support ecosystem modelling for MPAs management.

Benefits of exploiting the Blue-Cloud resources: The Blue Cloud platform was a crucial element in performing this pilot's work. Using the Open Science Platform (Virtual Labs), the team gained a deep understanding of how Chl-a datasets functioned, which led to the idea of integrating the data. With the help of the Marine Copernicus Service, the team obtained the Blue-Cloud Chl-a 3D Model, which was then implemented into the backend of "Wildlife Tracker." Thanks to the API connection, the tool can now perform light memory processing and fast visualization. As a result of this research rooted in Blue Cloud, version v0.3 of the Wildlife Tracker product can now offer ocean datasets. The collaboration with Blue Cloud has also made the product reliable for future use in marine conservation projects.

An additional pilot that exploited the VLab resources is the **Marine Analyst** one. The main idea behind "Marine Analyst" was to extract valuable insights from environmental big data. To achieve this, the team created an open notebook, an open access API designed to help computers learn from the data, and a proof of concept that could address knowledge gaps. The Marine Analyst use case specifically focused on analysing 20 years of Chl-a archives at the global scale and identifying patterns in Chl-a fronts. Chl-a fronts are areas where the concentration of chlorophyll is high,

indicating the presence of phytoplankton and potentially serving as important feeding grounds for marine animals. By analysing these fronts, the Marine Analyst team hopes to gain a better understanding of the marine ecosystem and inform conservation efforts.

2.2. VLab “Plankton Genomics”

The aim of the plankton genomics demonstrator is to assess plankton functional distribution through a deep mining of biomolecular correlated with environmental data, through cutting edge machine learning.

<p>Partners: EMBL-EBI VLIZ</p>
<p>Main Target Users: Plankton researchers, ocean modellers, data product developers and Blue Data infrastructures, for their data products catalogues and as use cases.</p>
<p>UN SDGs addressed: 13 Climate action, 14 Life below water </p>

Plankton diversity is considered an Essential Ocean Variable and an Essential Biological Variable; monitoring it is therefore important to understand the health of our oceans. The Vlab offers two notebooks. One explores the clustering of a massive genomic dataset and its taxonomic and functional annotation. The other uses machine learning to relate those clusters to the environment (and their parameters such as longitude/latitude, temperature, pH) and extrapolate their potential distribution worldwide:

- **Genomics Notebook:** The genomics notebook provides an extensive network of protein clusters from the ocean microbiome based on DNA sequences collected by the Tara Oceans expedition. The clustering is based on similarity of sequences found in Metagenomes Assembled Genomes (MAGs). Sequences are taxonomically and functionally annotated but the building of clusters also highlights the large proportion of sequences that cannot be annotated (i.e. ½ of the sequences).
- **Habitat Modelling Notebook:** The habitat modelling notebook queries the protein clusters for a list of functions/enzymes involved in certain biogeochemical processes. The relative abundance of the target clusters is related to environmental variables through Multivariate Boosted Regression Trees (MBRT) and the fitted model is used to predict the potential proportions of each over the world's ocean.

Data sources through Blue-Cloud

The “Plankton Genomics” VLab has been developed by exploiting the following data sources from the Blue-Cloud DD&AS or directly from the data repository.

Blue-Cloud interoperable data space Vlab "Plankton Genomics"

Genomics data

Chla climatology

Figure 12 Plankton Genomics data sources from the Blue-Cloud DD&AS

2.2.1. User trend

Over the last year, we can report the following usage statistics:

- on average 2 JupyterLab and 2 RStudio session per week; this is down compared to last year because (i) we finished exploiting the service ourselves (the paper resulting from the work is now in the final stage of review), (ii) there has not been hackathon that created particularly strong (albeit temporary) usage.

Figure 13 number of accesses to the Jupyter service in the Plankton Genomics VLab

- an average of ~80 catalogue sessions per month related to accessing the description of the services and of the resulting datasets, showing that most of the access is now concentrating on the outputs of the work, which is expected at this point in the project.
- two services are described in the catalogue (the two notebooks described above) and two datasets are published: (1) the protein functional clusters computed by Notebook 1, (2) maps of proportion of gene functions (in the case of carbon concentration mechanisms in picoeukaryotes), an application of Notebook 2. **The service will also be published by EMODnet.**

Figure 14 Number of accesses to the Plankton Genomics VLab

Figure 15 Evolution of the userbase in the Plankton Genomics VLab

2.2.2. Uptake, exploitation and exploitation potential

The 2 services proposed in this VLab are dependent on one another. The first one “prepares” and “organises” the raw Tara Ocean dataset in terms of protein clusters while the second one uses this protein cluster dataset through an habitat modelling. To do so, environmental data is useful and used which means that to propose to a user a common catalogue that includes both environmental data and genomics ones make sense. EMODnet proposes physical and biological data under the same common central portal but without homogenisation yet of these 2 kinds of data, Copernicus Marine does not have in its catalogue biological data (apart from few plankton data). Even if there is some important work to define metadata and information to associate to a global discrete in situ genomic product, the output of the the first service of this VLab could be a future product of such an data aggregator and/or operational service where user will be able to come and use, at once, physical, chemical and biological (genomic) data. The second service, the habitat modelling, is a good example of what can be proposed on VRE in other projects or in improved or future operational services.

The intended use of this work is to explore the diversity of biological communities in the pelagic ocean using the data provided by the relatively recent metagenomics sampling. This is how it has been leveraged during the Blue-Cloud hackathon. **This use is being picked up within other EU-funded projects such as AtlantECO and BiOcean5D**, among others, and will be expanded, thanks to this initial experience, in Blue-Cloud 2026, in tight partnership with those other projects. The paper resulting from the combination of the work in the two Notebooks should be published soon and will contribute to the dissemination of the approach.

2.2.3. Hackathon exploitation potential

The [AtlantECO hacc-Up team](#) has used AtlantECO and BlueCloud plankton distribution data to develop autonomous species distribution modelling tools and map aspects of the Atlantic Ocean ecosystem. The pilot joined the Challenge 1A: Understanding the Ocean - How might we map hotspots of plankton diversity and identify geographic gaps in our knowledge using currently available plankton data sets? The group tested Blue Cloud infrastructure and used Jupyter Notebooks to map, extrapolate and visualise data.

Given the quality of work performed, the “AtlantECO hacc-UP” team classified in the first 10 positions of the Blue-Cloud Hackathon.

Other Hackathon pilots exploited the service offer of the “Plankton Genomics” Virtual La, giving an idea of the potential exploitation opportunities of the Lab. They are:

- **GoPlankton.** Plankton diversity is essential to many critical marine processes, such as food web dynamics, nutrient cycling, carbon sequestration, and fisheries. Despite being defined at various scales (i.e., genetic, morphological, functional), the origin of plankton diversity remains unclear. The GoPlankton team sought to answer a fundamental question: can we identify the drivers of plankton diversity in the Atlantic using existing data? Specifically, they focus on taxonomic and functional diversity. Building on observations from terrestrial ecosystems, they hypothesised that low latitudes have higher biological diversity but lower functional diversity, and that the difference between these two decreases with increasing latitude. By leveraging the Blue-Cloud data, they aimed to provide a mechanistic understanding of observed diversity patterns, identify directions for quantitative research and data limitations, and provide data analysis that can be used in models to improve projections of ecological redundancy and ecosystem services in future oceans.

- **MapBGC.** MapBGC aimed to look for and map the diversity, abundance, and novelty of biosynthetic gene clusters (BGCs) using antiSMASH or BGC domains from the datasets.
- **VDeepLab.** The VDeepLab team was composed of data visualisation enthusiasts that plan to develop a visualisation tool to ease and facilitate the presentation of the biogeography of gene clusters related to selected metabolic pathways. By combining multiple views of genomic and environmental data along with the spatial projections of the modelled responses of gene clusters to environmental patterns, they planned to transform these data into actionable insights. Particularly, the team was interested in identifying the spatial presence of genes and gene clusters whose products can be used as nutraceutical and pharmaceutical components (bioactive metabolites, nutrients, infochemicals and toxins); genes that participate in metabolic pathways that could provide us with sustainable liquid energies such as biodiesel, and perhaps even hydrogen. Moreover, they aimed to predict the function of genes with unknown function based on their geospatial distribution and the clusters of genes with known functions that co-occur spatially, ultimately to advance our understanding of the biogeography of gene clusters and identify new bioprospecting opportunities.

2.3. VLab “Marine Environmental Indicators”

The VLab “Marine Environmental Indicators” provides support to analyse the quality of the marine environment and inform decision makers about the good environmental status in a changing climate.

<p>Partners: </p>
<p>Main target users: environmental protection agencies and international stakeholders involved in the environment management.</p>
<p>UN SDGs addressed: 13 Climate action, 14 Life below water </p>

The VLab offers a web user interface and several scientific-based algorithms, that can be used to obtain environmental indicators and added-value data applying big data analysis and machine learning methods on multi-source data sets:

- **MEI Generator:** The Marine Environmental Indicators Generator service is a web graphical interface for the exploitation of multiple data sources with multiple algorithms, that allows the user to generate and display value-added environmental data from generic marine data.
- **Ocean Patterns & Ocean Regimes Indicators:** Ocean Patterns and Ocean Regimes indicators are based on machine learning methods. They consist in applying an unsupervised classification to profiles or time-series. Data are automatically gathered into clusters, depending on their vertical or temporal structure. When analysing the different clusters, spatial or temporal coherence can be revealed.

- **Storm Severity Index (SSI):** The SSI service calculates maps and time series of exceptional atmospheric wind or storm circumstances. Individual storms (Event SSI) and specific areas (Area SSI) can be calculated for a given time period and time step (for time series). Wind speed threshold data are used to relate the storm severity to specific impact (e.g. sea circulation, coastal damage).
- **Simple Access to Carbon Data:** The service provides information on how to use ERDDAP servers to access and retrieve subsets of inorganic carbon data in their preferred format, removing the need to download large file(s) that the user may not be interested in.

Data sources through Blue-Cloud

The “Marine Environmental Indicators” VLab has been developed by exploiting the following data sources from the Blue-Cloud DD&AS or directly from the data repository.

Figure 16 Marine Environmental Indicators data sources from the Blue-Cloud DD&AS

2.3.1. User trend

This vLab was initially focusing on the Mediterranean region, and progressively moved to take under consideration in its implementation the global ocean. This evolution is well represented in user statistics, because the majority of users are around the Mediterranean, however all the continents are actually present with registered users.

Figure 17 MEI Generator VLab average session overview

In terms of number of users, the biggest jump was during the Blue-Cloud hackathon, moving from 76 (Dec/2021) to 155 (Mar/2022), and finally reaching the number of 197 users in Mar/2023.

Figure 18 Evolution of the userbase of the MEI Generator VLab

Figure 19 Number of accesses to the MEI VLab

Throughout the whole period, Jupyter Notebooks were always available for the users, and the statistics show a continuous use of them, and also a cumulative higher level of interest in 2022, when all the foreseen notebooks were finally available.

2.3.2. Uptake, exploitation and exploitation potential

The MEI generator service and the associated methods inside the Analytics Engine, have been continuously used, especially in periods close to relevant events, contributing to rise the popularity of this VLab's aim, which is specifically targeting the implementation of an effective scientific based service for the needs of environmental protection agencies.

The first (MEI Generator) and last service (Simple Access to Carbon Data) of this VLab propose technical tools while the other 3 ones (Ocean Patterns & Ocean Regimes Indicators and the Storm Severity Index) are more scientific. The MEI generator is a web user interface that "ingests" full datasets to provide average, tendency, number as outputs. The prototype that calculates means over area and time is planned to be enhanced by including the 2nd (oceanic patterns depending on vertical and temporal structure) and 3rd (maps of storms based on threshold) services proposed and later more services. It is a useful tool for users who need some key and synthetic information from large and complex datasets.

This tool is planned to be enhanced by integrated other services in the Blue-Cloud 2026 project.

2.3.3. Hackathon exploitation potential

The data gathered in this VLab have been exploited by a lot of Hackathon participants to build applications and solutions for predicting and mitigating the impact of climate change on the world's oceans, thus providing evidence of the potential exploitation and uptake opportunities of the

service.

The pilot applications proposed during the Hackathon are listed below.

- **Black swan finder.** The "Black swan finder" tool aimed to revolutionise the way environmental data is collected and analysed by leveraging a decentralised approach. By utilising Blue-Cloud's data sources, the tool proposed a central database to provide data for research purposes while collecting real-time and continuous data from smart target locations, such as the North Pole and Maldives coasts. To ensure traceability and efficiency, a cryptocurrency-based model using NFTs was suggested to transform environmental factors into meaningful and traceable transactions that can be stored on a blockchain. By turning the real environmental data into NFTs, the data can be visualised on a 3D virtual platform, creating a single puzzle where the data acts as the pieces.
- **[DataDolphin](#).** For those who are not experts in marine science, data analysis can be a difficult and complex task to undertake. That's why DataDolphin developed a user-friendly toolkit that consists of three parts: a data analysis tool that reveals the general connections between data points, a prediction tool that forecasts future trends, and a playful platform that allows anyone to explore marine data in an intuitive and engaging way. Thanks to their innovative work, the DataDolphin team has been ranked in the top ten positions and is making great strides in advancing our understanding of the blue environment.
- **EutroWarn.** Eutrophication, the accumulation of nutrients in estuaries and coastal areas due to human activities like industry and agriculture, poses a significant threat to marine ecosystems and aquatic communities. This results in an increase in algal growth, reducing the concentration of oxygen and causing carbon dioxide emissions that lower the water's pH level, leading to ocean acidification that can harm shellfish and other organisms. Additionally, harmful algal blooms (HAB) can occur, emitting toxic substances that can lead to animal mortality and human poisoning via seafood consumption and more. To tackle this issue, early warning systems for severe eutrophication states are essential. EMODnet, a data infrastructure federated by Blue-Cloud, provides the data necessary for such a system. In the EutroWarn project, the team explored the feasibility of novel machine learning algorithms that are trained and evaluated on historical EMODnet data, serving as an early warning system for severe eutrophication conditions in European coastal waters. EutroWarn include oxygen, pH, chl-a, nitrate, phosphate, salinity, and temperature, to extract patterns and detect early warning signals for upcoming severe conditions. The team used the popular Ocean Data View (ODV) software for data pre-processing and visualisation.
- **IndiCro the Creators.** Rising sea levels caused by climate change and human activities pose significant challenges worldwide. Predicting the magnitude of sea level rise is a difficult task, as is mitigating its negative impacts on coastal areas. To address these challenges, the Sea Level Rise Prediction (SLRP) project proposed an algorithm that combines tide gauge data from the Perpetual Mean Sea Level Service (PSMSL) with satellite observations from TOPEX/Poseidon, Jason 1, and Jason 2. The resulting predictions enable the development of appropriate facilities to mitigate the negative effects of sea water intrusion into coastal areas. The SLRP algorithm guides the sizing of facilities such as underground and ground collectors of flooded water with repumping and distribution systems, which is designed to match the predicted values. Moreover, the algorithm's outputs enable the generation of renewable energy from tidal sources and the production of drinking water through desalination processes. The SLRP concept was applied to the Indian coast area by IndiCro the Creators. By providing accurate predictions of sea level rise, the SLRP project enabled

the development of effective strategies for managing the negative impacts of rising sea levels on coastal regions worldwide.

- **Nereus.** It is recognised that climate change is causing severe impacts on global ecosystems, including marine ecosystems. Despite the difficulty of anticipating such changes, there are new technologies that may help to adapt to these conditions. Early warning mechanisms can be evolved to anticipate an effective response by detecting changes in the status of environmental indicators, which help to understand complex phenomena affecting global and marine ecosystems. Nereus developed a scalable solution that combines existing dataset models and analytical methods with other data sources, such as human activities (solar and wave energy power farms, artificial islands developed in proximity, artificial rains used to control climate change in the proximity of interested marine areas, etc.).
- **Ocean Warning.** The objective of the "Ocean Warning" project was to establish a warning system for extreme marine events. This will be achieved by utilising various Copernicus products, including remote-sensing or modelling. The system focused on a selected ocean location and detected the occurrence of extreme events, such as marine heatwaves. Upon detection of such events, the system generated a summary report and issued appropriate warnings to alert relevant authorities and stakeholders.
- **OceanEmerge.** The effects of changes in the marine ecosystem are complex and become more complicated with the inclusion of anthropogenic drivers. Effective communication of the cause and effect relationship is necessary at two levels: policymakers require an understanding of the concepts to make informed legislative decisions, while those reliant on marine resources need up-to-date information for day-to-day operations. However, communicating this information can become complex, as each audience requires different levels of information resolution. To address this issue, a more interactive-based tool was proposed, to explore environmental scenarios in a clear and communicative manner on a single platform. The tool included indicators of primary productivity, species abundance, and the most common anthropogenic drivers of ecosystem change to be projected based on the current IPCC climate scenarios. The tool was designed to focus on the Mediterranean Sea.
- **Sea Guardians.** The idea proposed was to create an open map of the current conditions of the Mediterranean Sea and the possible scenarios that could occur by merging data and variables. This interactive tool provided users with the opportunity to explore the potential impacts of climate change on the Mediterranean Sea.
- **The Perches.** The Perches team sought to develop an online interactive and accessible dashboard, allowing for the real-time assessment of current and predicted environmental conditions and associated risks to coral habitats. The initial version was tailored to the Great Barrier Reef, but the team's ultimate goal was to create a framework that can be extended to coral habitats around the world.

2.4. VLab “Fish, a matter of scales” services

The objective of this VLab is to deliver a scalable and robust open data portal for fisheries in EU waters and beyond, with a focus on the Global Tuna Atlas and the Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries (GRSF).

Partners: FORTH INSTITUTE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE

Main Target Users: Fisheries resource managers and fisheries research community, traceability experts and the general public.

UN SDGs addressed: 2 Zero hunger, 13 Climate action, 14 Life below water

The VLab offers two independent services; the fisheries atlas (with Global Tuna Atlas as an example), and the Global record of Stocks and Fisheries that consist of a combination of a semantic knowledge base and data-flow, and a data integration service.

Both services rely on ISO-OGC compliant data-flows and expose data in a catalogue and metadata-driven map viewer with R-Shiny components to expose data to the general public. Registered users can also access data using R, Jupyter notebooks, and data miner:

- **FIRMS Tuna Atlas:** The FIRMS Tuna Atlas is one result of the Fisheries Atlas service. The service behind is a mature Spatial Data Infrastructure that is also used in Demonstrator 5. The service allows to harmonise and standardise fisheries data to become uniform global datasets. This requires a complex workflow that has to be validated with the data providers in order to ensure high-quality datasets.
- **Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries:** Ocean Patterns and Ocean Regimes indicators are based on machine learning methods. They consist in applying an unsupervised classification to profiles or time-series. Data are automatically gathered into clusters, depending on their vertical or temporal structure. When analysing the different clusters, spatial or temporal coherence can be revealed.

Data sources through Blue-Cloud

This VLab has been developed by exploiting data sources from the Blue-Cloud DD&AS, which are summarised here below:

Figure 20 Fish, a matter of scale data sources from the Blue-Cloud DD&AS

The services in this VLab rely more on the BlueCloud provisioning service than on the data discovery and access services, and the VRE's are fully reliant on Blue cloud / D4Science technology for managing and delivering the enabling services.

2.4.1. User trend

The Bluecloud VRE are important for the fishery community to develop and test services. When services are 'community-proof' they are no longer considered Blue-Cloud services, but are exploited outside the Blue-Cloud computational context. This reflects on the exploitation of the Blue-Cloud services.

The growth of the Fisheries atlas users follow the community development effort. The peak in June 2022 is linked to the moment when new data were prepared, and in February 2023 in occasion of the launch of the Blue cloud 2026 project, where the Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries (GRSF) and the Fisheries Atlas (FA) VLabs developed in pilot Blue-Cloud will be extended to capture fisheries data and environmental parameters on a global scale.

Figure 21 user trend for the Fisheries Atlas Vlab

The Fisheries Atlas is heavily reliant on R Studio, and the access number of R show that there were development spurts in summer last year and that the use of R Studio continues also this year. This indicates that the development continues, as the resulting innovations of the developments are often deployed in VRE’s that use the same technology as Blue Cloud, but are deployed in parallel.

Figure 22 R Studio accesses on the Fisheries Atlas VLab

Figure 23 Example image of the Fisheries Atlas showing a.o. a metadata driven projection of data from Remote sensing tracking mission with EMODNet bathymetry as base map, and a 3-d projection (non Eurocentric)

2.4.2. Uptake, exploitation and exploitation potential

In Blue-Cloud, services were refined to harmonize and standardize the collation of global fisheries statistics using a Geospatial data approach. The services can use D4Science for data mining to deploy WPS services that the community needs for (meta)data services. This has resulted in various products such as the Global Tuna Atlas and geospatial data workflows that are now in use by IRD and FAO. The services will be maintained with in-kind FAO inputs and through IRD’s program including through Blue-Cloud 2026.

The GRSF PRE is a dedicated VLab to validate the submission of new content in the GRSF Knowledge Base. The GRSF team uses this environment to validate new data harvests from the GRSF sources before these are published into the GRSF Admin and GRSF VREs. The GRSF pre is an active area where data are vetted before they are published in public VREs. The data of 3 data-providers with multiple datasets needs to be aligned and harmonized, and the semantic KB of FORTH needs to be provided with accurate information. This VRE provides a secure working environment for select staff working on these data. The VRE is also used to properly manage fishing areas, based on the legal texts and descriptions of fisheries management organisations. The secure and confidential data management capacities of the infrastructure are essential in developing and sharing this sensitive information.

This VLab is a good illustration of the possibilities that D4Science VRE’s offer when data are harmonised. Two complementary services are the fisheries atlas (of tuna) and the Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries that share many features for statistical and geospatial data management. They achieve this even when some data is confidential and can be edited by authorised users (from FAO and other contributing organisations). The interesting point is that this VLab uses open data as the other V Labs, as well as confidential data; all the developments in the V labs remain closed as well as its access until data are ready to be released in a public repository.

The objective of the VLab to have confidential data management until data are ready to be published as FAIR open data for the general public can be validated by accessing

- the FAO Tuna Atlas released the first time in 2021 and accessible at <https://www.fao.org/fishery/geoserver/tunaatlas/>
- the GRSF Public VRE services maintained and operated by the iMarine initiative. The catalogue is accessible at <https://i-marine.d4science.org/web/grsf/data-catalogue;> the map viewer is accessible at <https://i-marine.d4science.org/web/grsf/map-viewer>.

The VRE approach has caught on in FAO, and similar data-workflows are used in several SDG14.4.1 related products such as the SDG14.4.1 VRE and the SOFIA-TAF VRE (operated by iMarine) that have been used to train hundreds of people on the use of stock assessment methods in a EU funded infrastructure.

Figure 24 examples of FAO VREs that are using the Blue-Cloud VRE approach

2.5. VLab “Aquaculture Monitor”

This VLab supports a workflow spanning Blue-Cloud and CLS infrastructures to produce maps based on Copernicus data. The VLab shows how Blue Cloud can integrate ISO-OGC products in a VLab.

Partners:
Main Target Users: Remote sensing data product developers and Blue Data product managers.
UN SDGs addressed: 2 Zero hunger, 13 Climate action, 14 Life below water

The VLab offers two independent services; one for cage detection, the other for land-type classification. The first service is implemented as a Jupyter notebook in the Blue-Cloud infrastructure to analyse S1 data over an area of interest, while the second interoperates with a CLS proprietary service that applies AI to S2 images. The results are accessible through a Blue-Cloud VLab that provides a map viewer:

- **Aquaculture Cage Detection:** The Jupyter notebook for aquaculture cage detection generates GEOPACKAGES over an ROI using Copernicus Sentinel 1 images. The first step is a tiling service to prepare the data for analysis, while in the second step the cages are detected. The output is ingested the Spatial data infrastructure that supports the VLab and is managed through D4Science, and shown in the ISO/OGC compliant Map viewer in the

Aquaculture VLab.

- **Aquaculture Ponds Detection:** The VLab ingests AI based land-types classifications as GEOPACKAGES over an ROI that provided the base for a validation based on in-situ data. The Blue-Cloud approach showed the technical feasibility to interoperate with external proprietary software and bring the results in a collaborative environment. The results can be mashed up with other Blue-Cloud products.

Data sources through Blue-Cloud

The workflow uses Copernicus data services. It combines the output in a ISO/OGC compliant spatial data infrastructure in a Blue Cloud VRE that can be used to discover and access Blue-Cloud datasets. Most of the technical work using the Blue Cloud was completed before 2022. In 2022, the activity focused on validating the results and testing AI services that use Copernicus data to classify land-types and aquaculture ponds. The maps are made accessible in the Blue Cloud using the same Spatial Data Infrastructure approach and services as the one successfully deployed for the fisheries atlas, thus showing the advantages of the Blue cloud approach for these demonstrators.

The metadata-driven Spatial Data Infrastructure behind the aquaculture Atlas and the Fisheries Atlas is capable of accessing EMODNet and other spatial data if these are FAIR and ISO/OGC compliant. It is now for instance possible to access EOv data near an aquaculture farm (see screenshot below)

Figure 25 example of combination of datasets via the Aquaculture monitor

The data exploited by this VLab through Blue-Cloud is graphically represented in the Figure below.

Figure 26 Aquaculture monitor data sources from the Blue-Cloud DD&AS

2.5.1. User trend

The data for the first sub-case, on aquaculture cage detection, uses copernicus sentinel-1 radar data products that were accessed directly. The analysis used a Jupyter notebook, and data results are pushed into the Blue-Cloud VLab using the same Spatial data infrastructure as for the Fisheries Atlas.

The second case accessed Sentinel 2 optical images directly and the test case used an AI approach that is not yet available in the infrastructure. The outputs were pushed to the Blue-Cloud VRE where they can be merged with other data from the ROI for further analysis.

The VLab was completed in October 2022 and since the case will not be carried forward in Blue-Cloud 2026, its use is not actively promoted and this results in a flattening curve of data accesses.

Figure 27 Number of accesses to the Aquaculture monitor

2.5.2. Uptake, exploitation and exploitation potential

Although this VLab has been finalised at the end of 2022 and that the second service is not opened to users because it was developed using a CLS proprietary service, the Vlab has some interest. It uses 2 kinds of satellite data: Sentinel 1 radar and Sentinel 2 optical images which in addition to in situ data and modelling ones from the previous V Labs complete the range of possibility and gives a good illustration of the VRE D4Science capacity and performance. **And even as a first stage prototype, this VLab shows the possibility of very specific and pragmatic applications from generic marine data from European providers or data aggregators directly to support fishery management.**

2.5.3. Hackathon exploitation potential

The data gathered in this VLab inspired the two first winning teams of the Blue-Cloud Hackathon. PerfeCt - Performance of Aquaculture under Climate change Hackathon team to formulate their use case on the potential impact of seawater-borne diseases on aquaculture sites. They conceived an application that would merge Blue-Cloud cage locations and Ocean current data to develop a risk map based on overall risk and after first detections for aquaculture farmers. The other winning team, Sea clearly, aimed at using aquaculture farm cluster locations to predict the impact from and on pollution by looking at ocean currents as a transport mechanism for e.g. microplastics. Their simulations can predict where pollutants can be expected, and thus help in site allocations and risk-monitoring of pollution. Their ideas can become a very concrete contribution to a safe, healthy, productive, predictive and transparent Ocean and are further described below.

Sea Clearly: Blue-Cloud Hackathon 1st Place application

The overall aim of the Sea Clearly pilot was to provide the locations and conditions for safer, pollutant-free fish to be farmed in aquaculture cages. This will result in higher yields and better food security.

The challenge: Aquaculture plays a critical role in meeting the challenge of feeding an ever-growing population while reducing the environmental impacts of food production. It has surpassed traditional fisheries as the primary source of fish for human consumption. However, aquaculture can also pose risks to the marine environment, and it is vulnerable to various marine events that can adversely impact its productivity. As responsible stewards of the environment, the Sea Clearly team aims to make informed decisions about aquaculture to ensure that we can feed the world's population without harming the ocean.

The Sea Clearly team joined **Challenge 2B: Maximising food return, minimising risks**. *Where might we place floating aquaculture farms in open and wild seas to get maximum “food return” with minimum risks?*

Services: Sea Clearly offers 2 services to the marine community:

- **Jupyter notebook:** The Jupyter notebook consists of forward and backward in time simulations of marine plastic visualising the impact of plastic from aquaculture cages on MPAs, and the most likely sources of plastic pollution affecting aquaculture cages in the Mediterranean Sea. CMEMS data is used to advect the simulated plastic particles and the aquaculture cages and MPAs locations are obtained from EMODnet.
- **Online simulation:** The website seaclearly.io is a service with the aim of showing interested members of the public the impact of plastic to and from aquaculture cages. It shows stakeholders the potential of the Sea Clearly tool without having to install it first. This service uses ParticleViz software. It uses pre-loaded simulations to and from a number of selected farms. It works on mobile devices making it accessible for any user with a connection to the internet.

Team members:

- Delphine Lobelle (Belgium) - Team lead
- Laura Gomez Navarro (Spain) - Co-developer
- Darshika Manral (the Netherlands) - Team member
- Cleo Jongedijk (the Netherlands) - Team member
- Joey Richardson (the Netherlands) - Co-developer
- Olmo Zavala (Mexico) - Visualisation expert
- Claudio Pierard - Co-developer
- Victor Onink (the Netherlands) - Co-developer

Benefits of exploiting the Blue-Cloud resources: The Blue-Cloud data and virtual lab platform allows Sea Clearly to share the tool with co-developers and with the public without the need for access to protected institutional data and/or computing resources. The team found that although using their institutional computational resources resulted in a quick start-up and initial development, sharing it across institutions even within the core development team required different setup/packages/data structures for every server/system. This means there is a barrier of knowledge on how to set-up a virtual research environment and how to download and install data and packages which need to be re-invented and developed for every institutional server setup and user. By using the Blue-Cloud platform, it ‘looks the same’ for all users from all institutions and

backgrounds which can be documented to help users with less computing skills to set-up and play around with the tool and the Blue-Cloud as a whole. Attracting more users of more variable backgrounds will, in the end, be beneficial for the development of the final product as well as for the Blue-Cloud and connected services itself.

PerfeCt: Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2nd Place application

PerfeCt, Performance of Aquaculture under Climate Change, is an innovative pilot that helps stakeholders establish and/or adapt aquaculture sites in the face of climate change.

The challenge: Using a modular geospatial web application, the pilot provided a set of expected attributes that can help estimate aquaculture performance on a given location for a desired IPCC climate change scenario. This information can help aquaculture producers optimise their production strategies, reduce risk, and minimise environmental impact.

The PerfeCt team joined the **WILDCARD - Hack the Blue-Cloud! - Challenge 4**.

Team members:

- Ines Haberle (Croatia) - Team lead
- Tamara Djerdj (Croatia) - Team member
- Branimir Hackenberger (Croatia) - Team member
- Tin Klanjscek (Croatia) - Team member
- Domagoj Hackenberger (Croatia) - Team member
- Nina Marn (Croatia) - Team member
- Bruno Čaleta (Croatia) - Team member
- Marija Purgar (Croatia) - Team member
- Jadranka Pecar Ilic (Croatia) - Team member
- Damir Kapetanović (Croatia) - Team member

Benefits of exploiting the Blue-Cloud resources: The application relies on a range of different types of open-source data such as Copernicus temperature available through Blue-Cloud, while at the same time the project contributed by bringing new data on locations of fish farms and MPAs – available up to that point only through Croatian governmental repositories – and putting them available through Blue-Cloud to broader audience. The team also integrated the ‘Add-my-pet database’ containing parameters of dynamic energy budget (DEB) models for more than 900 fish (and more than 3300 animal species overall). Another contribution is that the code underlying the application, containing equations for both fish DEB and Vibrio growth models, was made freely available through Blue-Cloud, making it accessible to anyone interested in exploring, reusing, or expanding the code.

Additional pilot applications proposed during the Hackathon that exploited the 2 fisheries demonstrators are listed below.

Aquamap. Aquaculture farming is becoming increasingly important in the seafood industry as a means of feeding a growing world population. However, farmers are facing risks from various factors such as climate change, pollution, and extreme weather events. Choosing the right location for a fish farm is a difficult decision as it needs to be both productive and environmentally safe. Unfortunately, there are limited tools to help farmers and policy-makers make informed decisions.

The aquamap team is currently working on a project to create maps that show the best locations for fish farming. They are gathering data on ocean characteristics such as temperature, nutrient levels, and risks and benefits associated with specific locations. By analysing this data with advanced computer programs, they will produce clear and easy-to-read maps that will help farmers and policy-makers make better decisions. The maps will provide insight into the best places for fish farming, while minimising the risks and environmental impacts. The team is also exploring different ways of presenting the data to provide the most useful information possible. This project aims to promote sustainable and responsible fish farming practices to help feed the world population.

Blue T(win). Modern societies have a T-shaped knowledge structure, where expert knowledge is concentrated within narrow scientific fields while public insights are often limited to a self-referential horizontal layer. The drive towards multidisciplinary and big data approaches can further widen this gap. Bridging the divide between science and the public can be facilitated by developing data products with clear narratives for stakeholders. To address this issue, a mini project was proposed to explore the potential of a Front End Experience Blue T(win) in extending the Blue-Cloud initiative and technology. The project aimed to investigate how various marine data products can be integrated to provide meaningful insights to the public. By developing a user-friendly interface and utilising appropriate algorithms, the project aims to provide stakeholders with easy access to relevant data and insights. This helps connect science with the public, and facilitate informed decision-making related to aquaculture and other marine activities.

TeamCoral. The TeamCoral team aimed to compare the environmental impact before and after the construction of an aquaculture farm. By analysing the changes in the environment and assessing the impact of the farm on the surrounding ecosystem, the pilot project aimed to provide useful insights into sustainable and responsible aquaculture practices. By analysing the data gathered during the environmental impact assessment, the project team identified areas where improvements can be made in terms of minimising negative impacts and maximising the benefits of aquaculture farming. The goal was to promote sustainable and efficient aquaculture practices that are both environmentally friendly and economically viable.

3. Uptake of the DD&AS

The **Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access service**⁷ is a one-stop-shop with a common interface to data sets and data products from many leading **Blue Data Infrastructures**⁸, which has potential for further expansion. It facilitates discovery and retrieval of data sets and data products for external users in stand-alone mode, and for users of the VRE through connectivity. These data sets are managed in the blue data infrastructures that are connected to the Blue-Cloud service to serve federated discovery and access.

Figure 28 Blue-Cloud data federated framework

The overall concept is that the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access service makes use of web services and APIs, following protocols such as CSW, OAI-PMH, ERDDAP, or otherwise, as provided and maintained by the blue data infrastructures. These are used to support machine-to-machine interactions for harvesting metadata, submitting queries, and retrieving resulting metadata, data sets and data products. As a result, a common interface (GUI) is offered for discovery and retrieval of data sets and data products from each of the federated blue data infrastructures. The GUI also includes facilities for mapping and viewing the locations of data sets, as part of the query dialogue.

The developments for the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access service have resulted in launching of the β -version in the middle of June 2021. Since that launch, further developments have taken place for adding functionality and refining specific parts of the service. The operational Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access service facilitates users:

- to search and discover interesting data sets;
- to complete and submit a shopping basket with interesting data sets;
- to stay informed about the progress of the shopping requests;
- to download the data sets once ready for downloading;

⁷ <https://blue-cloud.org/services/blue-cloud-data-discovery-and-access-service>

⁸ <https://www.blue-cloud.org/data-infrastructures>

- to ingest data sets into the VRE data pool for use in VRE applications.

And it facilitates managers of blue data infrastructures to stay informed about the shopping requests and associated users for their repository.

The currently federated Blue Data Infrastructures are: EMODnet Chemistry, EurOBIS, SeaDataNet, EuroArgo and Argo GDAC, ELIXIR-ENA, EcoTaxa, ICOS-Marine and SOCAT.

The uptake by users is given in the following two images:

Figure 29 No of users divided over countries

Figure 30 No of downloaded data sets per Blue Data Infrastructure

In practice, the uptake of the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access service by users has so far been slow, despite promoting it at various occasions and as part of the overall Blue-Cloud promotion and marketing activities. While from a technical perspective, there has been quite an interest and

positive feedback from fellow developers. A comparable experience has been noted by its developers for other new discovery and access services in the marine domain, such as the SeaDataNet CDI service which first took quite some time to get accepted and used, while it is nowadays an essential component of e.g. EMODnet and annually serves many hundreds of users, delivering to them millions of data sets. It is expected that this is also going to happen for the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access service, in particular because in the framework of the Blue-Cloud 2026 project its federated offer and query functionalities will be expanded and overall more outreach will be deployed for the project and its core services.

4. Usage of the new VLabs

4.1. JONAS

The JONAS VLab is developed as a pilot supporting the JONAS Project - Joint Framework for Ocean Noise in the Atlantic Seas initiative. The VLab offers to any JONAS user a working environment for Blue-Cloud tools and data to further their research and application needs (Access is restricted to project users only).

The number of users of this VLab is limited (7 registered users in Feb. 2023) and it is not expected to significantly grow in the future since the environment was mainly conceived to facilitate the dialogue among the two initiatives.

A screenshot of the environment is in the figure below.

Figure 31 Overview of the JONAS Vlab within the Blue-Cloud VRE

4.2. JERICO

The JERICO CORE VLab was developed as a pilot supporting the collaboration between Blue-Cloud VRE and the JERICO Coastal Oceans Resource Environment (JERICO CORE). The VLab offers to any JERICO user a working environment for JERICO CORE tools and data to further their research and application needs (Access is restricted to project users only).

This VLab has been in operational status since December 2021. The number of users of this VLab is limited (16 registered users in Feb. 2023) since the environment was mainly conceived to facilitate the dialogue among the two initiatives and investigate the spectrum of technical interoperability of the services. As a consequence of this collaboration and after successfully testing the offered facilities, during the Blue-Cloud 2026 initiative the JERICO team will integrate the JERICO-CORE services (such as Notebooks) via the dedicated VRE set-up during the Blue-Cloud project.

A screenshot of the environment is in the figure below.

About JERICO CORE VLab

JERICO CORE
SCIENCE - SERVICES - SUSTAINABILITY

The JERICO CORE Virtual Lab is an element of the JERICO Coastal Oceans Resource Environment (JERICO CORE).

JERICO CORE supports the development of a European gateway to long-term scientific observations and applications. It provides services for European coastal marine systems at the convergence between the land, open ocean, and atmosphere. JERICO adopts a systematic approach to monitor ...

[See more](#) [Edit this text](#)

Other options ...

Invite Members

[Send Invite](#)

VRE Managers and Groups

[View Managers](#)

JupyterHub

JupyterHub enables the exploitation of computational environments and resources without burdening users with installation and maintenance tasks. This JupyterHub environment is (i) preconfigured with libraries and packages to ease the execution of common data analytics tasks, and (ii) provides access to the Workspace enabling sharing of resources much easier.

RStudio

RStudio provides an integrated development environment for R. It includes a console and a syntax-highlighting editor and it enables code execution. Tools for plotting are also included. This RStudio environment is (i) preconfigured with libraries and packages to ease the execution of common data analytics tasks, and (ii) provides seamless access to the Workspace enabling sharing of resources with other members much easier.

Notes for the exploitation of this VLab

Development and integration environment for R, Python, and other supported software languages

START

- It is powered by a cluster of Analytics Engine servers, each with 16 cores and 32 GB RAM.
- It is powered by a cluster of RStudio servers, each with 16 cores and 32 GB RAM.
- It is powered by JupyterHub with a maximum of 8 cores and 32 GB RAM per notebook. JupyterHub is provided by D4Science with the support of EGI.eu.

All the environments are not for large-scale processing. They are conceived to support the integration, testing, and validation of your script in the D4Science distributed computing facility.

Data Discovery

Data Discovery and Access service

Facilitates discovery and retrieval of data sets and data products for external users in stand-alone mode. The Blue-Cloud data sets are managed in blue data infrastructures that are connected to the Blue Cloud service to serve federated discovery and access.

[Visit the service](#)

JERICO CORE [Recent](#)

Name	Owner	Last modified
my different folder	AR	20 Dec 16:45:21

Figure 32 Overview of the JERICO VLab within the Blue-Cloud VRE

5. Conclusions

Over the last 42 months the Blue-Cloud consortium has projected the original *pilot platform* to a strategic component of the *European Open Science Cloud*, a best practice for *Data federation* in Europe, a needed infrastructure for the nascent *European Digital Twin of the Oceans* framework and a scientific playground for the *EC Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030*. The effectiveness of the Blue-Cloud model was proven by five demonstrators that can actively contribute to the UN SDGs, whose services and datasets have been used and integrated in products now part of the offer of long-term Blue Data Infrastructures such as EMODnet Biology/EurOBIS, CMEMS, SeaDataNet, GEBCO, the World Ocean Atlas. Some of the products can also be accessed from external platforms to maximise the exploitation of the results, such in the case of Copernicus, IRD and FAO. The hackathon applications have shown the replicability and market potential of Blue-Cloud datasets and services for the Blue Economy, spamming use for the fisheries and aquaculture industry, eutrophication, climate change and societal impact linked to human activities. The partnerships with (26!) projects and initiatives in Europe and beyond demonstrated and assessed the accessibility of Blue-Cloud services, while facilitating usability and interoperability of resources, and boosting that spirit of collaboration that is at the core of European Research.

The architecture of the Blue-Cloud VRE proved to be scalable and sustainable, being fit for connecting additional e-infrastructures, implementing and integrating more and advanced blue analytical services, configuring more dedicated VLabs, and targeting broader (groups of) users.

The Blue-Cloud 2026 follow up initiative will introduce new ways for adopting additional cloud storage, cloud computing, deep learning and neural networks for supporting big data processes for validation, extraction, interpolation and products generation. Several data intensive WorkBenches for selected Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) will be developed and validated. Data scientists will be empowered with new classes of algorithms for the execution in the collaborative cloud environment offered by the Blue-Cloud VRE. The final aim of evolving the service offer and enlarging the number and type of users, this giving additional value to the impact illustrated in this and the other Blue-Cloud deliverables.